

Name:
LID/LG NAME:
Source(s):
Date completed:

Phonological Domains Questionnaire

Last Revision February 2005

Companion Questionnaire to "Grammatical Domains Questionnaire"

PREAMBLE:

The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather data on phonological patterns and constraints in forms of varying degrees of morphological complexity. In many languages there are prosodic constraints/rules that are not strictly defined by phonological domains, but that require attention to different morpho-syntactic domains (perhaps in somewhat idiosyncratic or very generalized ways). For this reason, the questionnaire is organized to gather information about processes that are sensitive primarily to phonologically defined domains, and *also* to gather information about those processes that include morphologically and syntactically complex domains.

Before you begin:

1. Give examples of each case described
2. When noting morpheme types, refer to the Leipzig glossing rules for glossing conventions (<http://www.eva.mpg.de/lingua/files/morpheme.html>)
3. Be sensitive to differences in phonemic (/CV/) and phonetic ([CV]) representation
4. Whenever possible, note behavior of **borrowed forms**

I. *Language Profile*

Reported number of speakers

Contact language(s)

Language status (official/lingua franca, private, special use, pidgin/creole koiné, etc.)

Language prospects (maintenance, shift, threatened, moribund/death, revival, etc.)

Structural results (light/medium/heavy lexical/structural borrowing, simplification, expansion etc.)

II. *Morpheme Types*

Give a list of the available inflectional/derivational morpheme types in this language. They may include: suffix, prefix, infix, circumfix, prosodic/non-concatenative/suprasegmental/ablaut formative, enclitic, proclitic, endoclititic, particle, stem position (e.g. of bipartite stems). This is important for the **domains** part of this questionnaire. The **domain** of a process = the morpheme types included in that process (e.g. stem only, stem ± suffix, stem + suffix + particle, etc.)

III. *Syllable*

Note all possible syllable types

If syllable has VV, does this = long vowel, diphthong, both?

Can a monosyllabic/monomoraic unit be a minimal free form? In other words, can it stand alone phonologically as a 'free word'? If yes, provide examples

Can a word really be vowel-initial and/or vowel-only? Note both lexical & non-lexical forms

Monomorphemic & polysyllabic forms: are phonological patterns identical to that of monosyllabic forms, or are there differences? Pay special attention to any variation in:

Phonotactics--word-medial consonant patterns vs. word-edge

Variations across lexical categories--nouns vs. verbs vs. adjectives

Does the language have *super-heavy syllables* (e.g. CVV; CVVC CVCC, etc.) If so, what types are there and what are their distributions in words of different morphological complexity?

IV. *Tone & Stress*

This may also be covered in other sections (e.g. suprasegmental processes or phonological patterns in polymorphemic forms)

If forms are *polymorphemic*, always specify the domains involved & excluded (e.g. stem ± suffix; not prefix, etc.)

If there is a pattern of *secondary* stress, note domains in the same way

Describe domains for stress, tone and/or intonation at "higher levels" if available (phrase, clause, sentence, utterance, etc.).

Note "specialized" instances of stress & the grammatical domains included (e.g. emphatic stress)

V. *Other Non-concatenative Processes*

Note morphological domains & limits of substitution, prosodic operations, stem modifications

For example: ablaut, subtractive, replacive, substitutive processes, tone, stress alternations, etc.

VI. *"Free" Grammatical Morphemes*

Here, the focus is the possibly strange or different degree of phonology between stem morphemes & 'less cohering' grammatical morphemes (e.g. patterns found with stem-clitic combinations, prefix-stem combinations, or with affix clusters)

Patterns/processes to note:

Syllable structure & phonotactic variations

Tone/stress (do they receive their own? Do they participate in tone/stress patterns with adjacent stem?)

Variations across morpheme types

VII. *Polymorphemic Stem forms*

(Exclude lexical allomorphy, e.g. allomorphy chosen on item-based principles like declension class, etc.)

Do *all* grammatical morphemes participate in the *same ways* in the below processes?

Phonotactics at and across morpheme boundaries

Allophonic alternations at and across morpheme boundaries

Shortening/lengthening at/across boundaries

Assimilation/dissimilation/harmony at/across boundaries

Place/manner/voicing/aspiration changes at/across boundaries

Fortition/lenition at/across boundaries

Tone/stress across or at different morph elements

Insertion/deletion at/across boundaries

Bipartite stems: they are discontinuous, monomorphemic stem words. They are discontinuous via affix interposition. Are they also *phonologically a single piece*? i.e. does phonology treat them like other disyllabic, monomorphemic words?

VIII. *Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions*

How are they like/different from polymorphemic stem + gramm, morpheme forms?

Phonotactics at boundaries

Alternations, processes, other changes at boundaries (e.g. deletion/insertion, assimilation/dissimilation, place/manner/voicing changes, etc.)

Tone/stress patterns in comparison to those seen in section IV.

Insertion/deletion at boundaries

Note differences for different compounding types (e.g. noun vs. verbal compounds)

IX. *Reduplication*

Function(s) of reduplication? (e.g. marks plural, aspect, emphatic, etc.)

Can the copied portion/domain be regularly specified/described (without exception)?

Is this portion *phonologically* (syllable, foot, total, etc.) or *morphologically* (affix, stem, root, etc.) specifiable? Note exceptions & idiosyncracies

Note any variations in copied portion, give examples (both pre- & post-duplication)

X. *Phrase/Sentence-level phenomena*

Intonation/prosody within and across phrases & clauses

Phrase-level, clause-level, sentence-level stress

Pause phenomena within or across these domains

Special patterns/phenomena that apply only across syntactic units or at clause-level (e.g. elision, resyllabification, aspiration at these 'higher' boundaries)

XI. *Other Special things to look for*

Distribution of & constraints on geminates

Foot: is there evidence for the relevance of foot structure in a language, including stress and/or segmental patterns? (In other words, do syllables pattern together for certain processes, or can they be categorially sub-divided/distinguished for processes in a way that highlights a phonological domain that is not a word, but rather something else?)

Note any *special exceptions* to the above processes (e.g. 1 particular suffix or 1 special lexical category that is different/non-participatory)

XII. *How to Use the Template in the Appendix*

This chart is designed to help you keep track of the phonological patterns/processes/rules found in a grammatical description (especially useful for languages with extensive concatenative morphology, or with multiple available morpheme types), and to note domains and the degree to which forms of varying morphological complexity participate in some phonological process, what is excepted, etc. Along with the processes, you can include "duplication" "nominal compounds", etc. under "Domains". You may want to modify the template to better suit the needs of the particular report (e.g. to track suprasegmental (e.g. "templatic") processes). For a language with many processes and/or extensive morphology, you may need to extend the template. For a specific case, see also the sample template for Meithei, a Tibeto-Burman language of India.